

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Beauty as Violation: Female Desire, Disposition and Destiny in the Select Short Stories of Ismat Chughtai

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ABSTRACT

At a time when India was still not ready to accept sexuality as a natural phenomenon or women's desire as a need, Ismat Chughtai wrote about these non-traditional themes without being overtly didactic in its undertones. She lays bare the true human nature in the most raw and unashamed manner through her narrations. The female desire, patriarchal control and marriage as a means of regulating how power is exercised form a large part of her oeuvre. This paper aims to show that female beauty and body become a site of surveillance, dominance, as well as a tool that threatens to destabilise the male ego. Drawing on her three short stories, 'Eternal Vine' (Amar Bel), 'The Rock' (Chatan) and 'The Wife' (Ghar Waali), which rely on the theatrics of marriage, it shows how women negotiate between the pain and pleasures of beauty, their own desire and presupposed disposition within the conjugal relationship.

Keywords: Female Beauty, Male Ego, Marriage, Desire, Discipline

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

In India, the "Colonial restructurings of gender and the curricular institutionalisation of literature..." (Tharu and Lalita 10) gave way to a kind of early postcolonial literature which, on one hand, offered limited space for female expression and censorship of erotic text, and on the other hand, considered only English literature as superior. During such a time, Ismat Chughtai entered the realm of Urdu literature with such clarity, conviction and authority that it sent ripples through the country's social, cultural and political atmosphere. Krishan Chander wrote the Foreword to Chughtai's first collection of short stories, *Choten*, in which he explains how the mention of Chughtai's name made some male writers mortified.

The publication of *Lihaaf* became a focal point of Chughtai's career. Critics strongly condemned the boldness of handling a subject matter that was supposed to be non-explicit, but she continued writing about taboo issues. "Ismat, like her contemporaries, was influenced by European fiction...Having greatly influenced Freud's theories of psychosexual development, the new writers also wrote freely and openly about certain aspects of human sexuality, but, as in the case of Ismat, with sincerity and intelligence" (Chughtai xii). She would not waste time tiptoeing around taboo issues. In both tone and style, Chughtai was bold; she also upheld the Indian middle-class sensibilities with maturity, and her portrayals of characters were realistic and vivid, even within the spatial constraints of short stories.

The three stories hinge on the idea of marriage, marriage as a tool for subjugation and how beauty, desire and honour operate within marriage. Naomi Wolf, an American feminist and author, wrote *The Beauty Myth*, in which she argues that beauty becomes a disciplinary tool used to control women. She writes, "The beauty myth tells a story: The quality called 'beauty' objectively and universally exists. Women must want to embody it, and men must want to possess women who embody it" (12). At the same time, she proposed these ideas in the 21st century, when women's flesh and skin have been commodified by consumerism; Chughtai, a century earlier, instilled similar ideas. The idea of female beauty serves as a double-edged sword in her stories, both disciplining and destroying. A careful study of her stories reveals that she sees marriage not as a custom but as an institution, where beauty acts as a currency systematically curated to suit the patriarchy. The female desire, male ego and the flimsy honour of the middle-class household, thus become important themes in her writing, and she handles the dynamics with maturity.

'Eternal Vine'

When the story begins, readers find that five sisters are fervently seeking a bride for their middle-aged widowed brother. The discussions around the house give the impression of a typical Muslim middle-class family, where a bride is brought in to serve the husband and sustain the bloodline. A teenage girl is selected for their brother without paying any heed to the disturbing age gap. 'She was slender and fragile', the reason Ruksana was chosen to marry their brother, as she perfectly fit within the constructed idea of feminine beauty. The idea of beauty runs on two levels- the physical beauty and the 'ideal' beauty. The physical beauty needs to wear off eventually, to maintain 'the ideal' beauty as an unreachable standard for women, something one can only wish or strive for but never fully become or accomplish. ...two or three children later, all the silver coating wears off. When surrounded by diapers, little will remain of this beauty, this colouring or the tiny waist. The arms won't stay as supple either. If she doesn't begin to look your age soon, you can punish me as you fit. (Chughtai 97).

Fate, however, had different intentions for Ruksana. Neither did she lose her beauty, nor the playfulness. With each passing year and each childbirth, Ruksana continued to flourish like a force of beauty that glowed from within; her aged husband burned with disdain. Towards the end of the story, the jealousy consumed him completely. When they could not control her, they started accusing her of having liaisons, seducing jinns who keep her beauty intact. "It was as if she had stopped growing older...Her sister-in-law felt their hearts being sawed" (100). Age is another tool used against women. Subjugation of women's bodies cannot be understood without the politics of ageism. Ageism often intersects with gendered norms of beauty to present young women as desirable as well as replaceable as they age.

Her beauty was no longer hers. It was only to serve them. In Chughtai's stories, beauty is not presented as an aesthetic; it becomes a tool- a double-edged sword in this case. Her beauty, which once attracted her husband, became a bane to his existence. While his jealousy consumed him, her peace radiated from within. According to Sander Lee Bartky, "A woman's skin must be soft, supple, hairless and smooth" (31), so the surveillance of women's bodies does not end with flesh, but it goes beyond to appearance and beauty. Within the middle-class sensibilities, the power structure is retained by making women internalise their domestic disposition. Ruksana in the story does not express any desire or hysterics. She repeatedly sustains her energy, which naturally crushes all the flimsy egos of men. There's a vine- amar bel- which has green serpentine tendrils. These tendrils entwine themselves around

the healthy, broad tree trunks and the vine burgeons by drawing sap from the tree. As it grows and flourishes, the tree begins to shrivel and die. (Chughtai 102).

Women are often considered dependent beings who need to cling to their male counterparts after marriage. Chughtai subverts this idea by equating the woman with the 'Amar Bel'. Beauty of Rukshana grows excessively like a wild vine; it can no longer be tamed. The natural trait of the vine cannot be cut off- growing is the inherent nature of the vine. Its strength hinges on such mystical roots that the vine's beauty becomes terrifying. Chughtai rewrites the use of beauty- instead of pleasing patriarchy, it proved to be fatal, a paradoxical weapon that breaks structures it is supposed to maintain.

'The Rock'

The story deals with the theme of gendered surveillance of the body and the erasure of women's identity within marriage. A girl whose parents feared that she might rebel for freedom dropped out of school and was married off. As a new bride, she enters the new house as a meek and naïve girl, then begins her husband's earnest embarkment of "moulding her into a homemaker" (Chughtai 199). Her identity gets dissolved, and what remains of her persona is 'Bhabhi'- a dutiful wife and a doting mother. While she busied herself with self-surveillance, her husband became attracted to a young girl who fitted the image of a modern, new-age woman.

"...Bhaiyya saw Bhabhi, liked her immensely, and then they were married. However, at that time she was as delicate and beautiful as a lily."

"So what happened to her after she got married?"

"What could have happened? Bhabhi is the mistress of her house, queen among her children, not a film actress..." (Chughtai 204).

Their entire conjugal relationship was based on Bhaiyya finding Bhabhi attractive; there was no love involved. As the attraction faded over time, Bhaiyya no longer showed interest in his wife. The lack of conjugal love and emotional absence left her occupied with household chores and child-rearing, while Bhaiyya went on to have affairs with 'more' desirable women. Chughtai constantly reminds the reader how women's desirability depended on their bodies and their ability to appease the male gaze.

In many ways, Chughtai was ahead of her feminist counterparts. She found the subservient mentality of women to be a flaw. "All through her life, she has protested against such false values and deceptions" (Biswakarma 60). She very well understood

that the female body is constantly susceptible to tension and surveillance, and tries to alert her readers about the dangers of body politics through her narration. "'Oh God, how fat you are!' Bhaiyya exclaimed" (Chughtai 207). In Bhaiyya's eyes, his wife's existence has been reduced to flesh and body that should be subject to rigid discipline. Women are made to feel ashamed of their bodies to keep them under control.

Michel Foucault, in his book *Discipline and Punish*, argues that in the modern, 'free' world, there are more nuanced means of control, through which a body is disciplined. "The body... is caught up in a system of constraints and privations, obligations and prohibitions" (Foucault 11). Although he failed to differentiate the disciplines peculiar to women's experiences, his ideas can be linked to understand how gendered bodies became a site of patriarchal dominance. The production of 'docile bodies' is done through systematic appropriation of regime control, where every movement of the body is monitored and regulated.

The man tries to produce a woman's body of a certain size and demeanour; anything outside the prescribed dimensions is seen as distasteful. Moreover, there are multiple ways in which a women's body is controlled. "'She proceeded to consume the apricot jam and cream with ardour...' 'That's enough!' he muttered, his nostrils flaring" (Chughtai 207). "Dieting disciplines the body's hunger: appetite must be monitored at all times and governed by an iron will" (Sander 28). Femininity requires obedience. Men's expectation of the ideal body image poses a burden on women for bodily perfection. She calculates and confines her diet so she does not betray the traits of desirability.

The application of makeup is also involved in the production of an ideal feminine image, as bodies are used as an 'ornamental surface'. Similarly, dressing up or wearing makeup can also be seen as a form of self-expression, a person exercising their agency. "She was a housewife, a daughter-in-law, and she was everyone's darling; why should she dress up and deck herself out like a prostitute to please people?" (Chughtai 200). In Bhabhi's case, not dressing up gives her a badge of acceptability, modesty and a sense of self-proclaimed character certificate. Thus, through such practices, a disciplined body is produced that fears any deviation may result in punishment conferred upon her through various means.

As Bhabhi, after childbirth, could no longer conform to the desirable body, she too was punished through the objective of divorce. Bhaiyya went on to marry another woman, yet the pattern repeats. The women around him wither away, as he drifts from

one woman to the next. He keeps chasing beauty until it becomes a burden. Like a rock has crushed waves, new and old, women around him are destined to fade away.

'The Wife'

The story charts the process of gradual transformation of Laajo, a harlot, into a 'Wife'- a socially accepted identity for a woman. When Mirza, an unmarried man, was suggested to shelter Laajo as a maidservant to perform his chores, he rebuked that idea. "God forgive me, I'm not accustomed to keeping women of low character in my house," (Chughtai 26). While he frequently visits prostitutes, the 'house' becomes a sacred place where the outcast cannot be permitted. Sexual promiscuity, as long as it is done outside the sanctity of the house, keeps his character intact.

When Laajo entered the household as a maidservant, Mirza was confronted with someone sure of her identity. Unlike Mirza, who was sceptical about his stance, Laajo had an air of certainty. She was sure about her sexual desires and was not concerned about the labels of society. He was seething with repressed sexual desires under the façade of social respectability. When Mirza could no longer delay his sexual urges, he gave in to his temptations. However, his sexual liaison with Laajo only increased his jealousy. Thus, to combat her self-assurance, he begins to cajole her.

"If you are mine, then marry me" (Chughtai 34). Men often see women as possessions, something to win over. He needed to own Laajo to control her body, mind and desires- and he presumed marriage could provide him with that opportunity. "She knew well the truth about herself – only virgins got married, and she couldn't remember a time when she had been a virgin. She wasn't fit to be anyone's wife" (Chughtai 35). Laajo was aware of the truth of her body, that her sexuality could violate the sanctity of marriage. A woman's body, which is not a virgin, is considered filthy. Judith Butler, in 'Gender Performativity' theory, argues that gender is an act that we perform according to social expectations. "The idea of gender is an act, or performance. This acts in the way a person walks, talks, dresses, and behaves" (Singh, 1981). Thus, for a woman to perform the role of 'wife' requires sexual purity and bodily restraints. Laajo's behaviour, her clothes, and her demeanour did not fit the assigned role of wife. The character of Laajo thus becomes an antidote to the accepted notions of a 'wife' and the performance that sustains that idea.

"What had once been Laajo's charm now became Mirza's bride's audacities" (Chughtai 36). Her identity was manipulated from being an individual to 'Mirza's bride'. However, the flimsy manners that usually uphold the respectability of a family were never enough to lower her spirits. Being a wife required Laajo to exchange her

desires for domesticity. When Mirza's project of 'building a wife' out of Laajo failed miserably, he decided to divorce her. Helene Cixous' essay "The Laugh of the Medusa" presents the idea that 'Medusa' was considered a monster because she does not abide by the rules. Any woman who cannot be controlled is made to feel ashamed. Here, too, Laajo could not be controlled, so she was made to feel ashamed of her identity, but she evaluates identity in terms of utility, not purity.

By reappointing Laajo as a maidservant in the household, Chughtai reveals his dependency trait and her survival instinct. Laajo's realisation that 'being a bastard has actually worked in her favour subverts the conventional value of dishonour being associated with illegitimacy. Further, Mirza's failure to confront his animal instincts is proof that the idea of honour is a cover for moral degradation. Laajo's resistance is pragmatic, as she uses her status to negotiate and confront the foundations of established structures, subtly wielding agency through a stigmatised body.

There is no common thread that unites these women in appearance, except that their beauty, bodies and desires are controlled by male supervision. In 'Eternal Vine' and 'The Rock', the female characters are not given much voice in the narration. It is a deliberate attempt by Chughtai to show how reality is decided for women, not by women. These women are made to practice self-disdain and self-shame. Ismat Chughtai thus shows that the relationship between female beauty and female liberation is paradoxical. Women who are considered 'unattractive' have to labour hard to appease the male gaze, while the ones considered ideal feminine beauty are told to avoid the male gaze. Laajo's character in 'The Wife' is an attempt at resisting the structure. Here, Chughtai presents the possibility of resistance by reclaiming the female desire and unsettling the authority. Thus, in Chughtai's world, 'beauty' is not just aesthetic, it is to be managed, performed and resisted; it is both an entrapment that restricts female liberation, as well as an agency that violates patriarchal mechanisms.

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